

SYNTHESIS AND ELASTIC AND ANELASTIC PROPERTIES OF (85C₆₀-15C₇₀)₈₀-(B₂O₃)₂₀ COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

It is known [1] that C₆₀ and C₇₀ fullerenes can form molecular crystals named fullerites. Fullerites are characterized by weak mechanical properties that do not allow us to prepare three-dimensional and mechanically strong fullerite samples.

In order to improve mechanical properties of fullerite materials, fullerite-based composites should be worked out. In such kind of composites the fullerite component forms a composite matrix and other component glues fullerite crystals together.

In this work we applied B₂O₃ oxide to prepare composite of (85C₆₀-15C₇₀)₈₀-B₂O₃ composition. B₂O₃ oxide has low melting temperature at ~700 K that preserves initial structure and properties of fullerites at composite fabrication.

2 Fabrication of composite and experimental methods

The (85C₆₀-15C₇₀)₈₀-B₂O₃ composite was synthesized via solid-state processing techniques from powders of the C₆₀ and C₇₀ fullerenes and the B₂O₃ oxide taken as starting materials. After preliminary milling and drying, mixture of powders was pressed at 5 GPa. The pressed samples were rapidly heating up to temperature at 670 K, then hold isothermally for 15 min at this temperature and finally quenched down to room temperature.

X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) was performed at room temperature for phase determination using a DRON-3.0 diffractometer with CuK_α radiation. Analysis of the XRD patterns allows us to conclude that the (85C₆₀-15C₇₀)₈₀-B₂O₃ composite is really fullerite-based material with face-centered cubic lattice (Fig. 1). Porosity of the composite was estimated to be equal to 32%.

For elastic (shear modulus G) and anelastic (internal friction Q^{-1}) experiments the setup based on the inverted torsion pendulum was used [2]. The measuring frequency was about 1 Hz and strain amplitude was $\sim 10^{-4}$. The samples under torsion pendulum experiments were in the form of 2x2x15 mm³ bars. Elastic and anelastic properties of the pure B₂O₃ oxide were also studied in order to distinguish a fullerite behavior in elastic and anelastic properties of the composite by comparison of the G and Q^{-1} temperature dependences of both materials.

3 Experimental results and discussion

The $G(T)$ and $Q^{-1}(T)$ dependences for the 85C₆₀-15C₇₀)₈₀-B₂O₃ composite (1 and 2 curves) and pure B₂O₃ oxide (1' and 2') taken at heating mode from 178 K up to 335 K with rate 0.5 K·min⁻¹ are presented in Fig.1 and Fig.2 respectively. One can see that these materials demonstrate very unlike behavior. So, elastic modulus of the composite increases at cooling with a small curvature of the $G(T)$ curve at the temperature $T_L=230$ K. Anomalous behavior around T_L can be also found in anelastic properties of the composite. No elastic and anelastic anomalies within the temperature interval under study were observed for pure B₂O₃ oxide.

For the 85C₆₀-15C₇₀)₈₀-B₂O₃ composite high-temperature background of elasticity at $T > T_L$ can be expressed as

$$G_b = G_0 - G_2 T^2 - G_4 T^4 \quad (1)$$

where G_0 , G_2 and G_4 are T -independent coefficients. The background line with $G_0 = 2.9$ GPa, $G_2 = -7.167 \cdot 10^{-6}$ GPa/K² and $G_4 = 1.578 \cdot 10^{-10}$ GPa/K⁴ is shown as a solid line in Fig. 2 (a).

After background line subtraction, anomalous contribution in elasticity, ΔG , below T_L can be considered in detail (Fig. 4).

One can see that the $\Delta G(T)$ dependence at $T < T_L$ is a line.

It is known that the C_{60} fullerite undergoes a structural phase transition from face-centered cubic lattice to primitive cubic structure below 250 K. Elastic and anelastic anomalies at T_L observed in the $(85C_{60}-15C_{70})_{80}-B_2O_3$ composite may be associated with structural phase transition in the fullerite matrix of the composite.

It is important to note that the internal friction of the composite is very strong changed from $0.95 \cdot 10^{-2}$ at 180 K up to $6.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ at 335 K. This strong increase of internal friction is also accompanied by strong elastic softening. Significant increase of the internal friction background at heating above $T > 0.5T_S$ (T_S is melting temperature of solid) is typical behavior for many solids. Usually such behavior is due to vacancies movements, interstitial atoms diffusion, incompressible dislocation movements in the field of alternative mechanical stresses.

The $Q^{-1}(T)$ dependence for the composite under study between 180 K and 335 K can be fitted by expression

$$Q^{-1} = \frac{A}{\omega^m T} \exp\left(-\frac{E_f}{kT}\right) \quad (2)$$

where A and m are constants, ω is angular frequency, E_f is energy of activation of the internal friction background and k is Boltzmann constant.

It was found that experimental $Q^{-1}(T)$ curve for the composite in the $\ln(Q^{-1} \cdot T) - (1/T)$ axes consists of two linear segments intersected at temperature $T_H = 290$ K (Fig. 5). Energy of activations for these segments were estimated to be equal to 0.19 ± 0.01 eV for $T < T_H$ and 0.06 ± 0.01 eV for $T > T_H$.

To explain the two energy of activations of the internal friction background we should take into account that the B and O atoms are able to occupy interstitial sites in the fullerite matrix by means of diffusion from the B_2O_3 oxide at high temperatures during the composite fabrication. In this case we can consider that for $T < T_H$ the internal friction change is connected with the O atoms and for $T > T_H$ the B atoms movements contributes to the internal friction background.

Another explanation of experimental results can be proposed. According to this explanation a migration only eigenvacancies within the fullerite matrix is taking into account. Then energy of activation of the internal friction background will consist of energy of

eigenvacancies formation and energy of these eigenvacancies migration.

Further experiments should be done to understand in detail the peculiarities of the elastic and anelastic properties of the $(85C_{60}-15C_{70})_{80}-B_2O_3$ composite.

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Fig. 1. XRD patterns for starting mixture of the $85C_{60}-15C_{70}$ fullerites (a) and for the $(85C_{60}-15C_{70})_{80}-B_2O_3$ composite (b)

Fig.2. Temperature dependence of shear elastic modulus for the $(85C_{60}-15C_{70})_{80}-B_2O_3$ composite (I) and the B_2O_3 oxide (I')

Fig.4. Temperature dependence of ΔG for the $(85C_{60}-15C_{70})_{80}-B_2O_3$ composite

Fig.3. Temperature dependence of internal friction for the $(85C_{60}-15C_{70})_{80}-B_2O_3$ composite (2) and the B_2O_3 oxide ($2'$)

Fig. 5. The $\ln(Q^{-1} \cdot T) - (1/T)$ dependence for the $(85C_{60}-15C_{70})_{80}-B_2O_3$ composite

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